

1 **Assessment of the effect of toothpaste abrasiveness**
2 **on friction and wear of dental fillings**

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14 Graphical abstract

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17 **Abstract**

18 There is a notable deficiency in detailed investigations regarding the impact of abrasive
19 elements on the friction and wear of dental restorations. Therefore, the primary objective of this
20 study was to analyse how abrasive particles in toothpastes affect the friction and wear of dental
21 fillings. The coefficient of friction (CoF) was evaluated as a time course from a brushing
22 simulation conducted on a UMT TriboLab tribometer, which measured frictional and normal
23 forces over a duration of 260 minutes. The tribological system consisted of three components:
24 a Curaprox Ultra Soft 5460 toothbrush, a sample of dental filling material, and a mixture of
25 artificial saliva (AS) combined with selected toothpaste. Six different toothpastes were
26 evaluated (four for adults and two for children), varying in relative dentin abrasivity (RDA)
27 values. Measurements with AS served as reference data. Wear was quantified by topographical
28 analysis using a Bruker Contour GT-X optical profilometer to assess the samples before and
29 after brushing, followed by volume loss calculations. Particle morphology was studied using
30 a Tescan MIRA3 microscope, and the element analysis of evaluated toothpastes was performed
31 using energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX). Results indicated that friction was highly
32 variable, influenced by the random presence of particles in contact. While wear and particle
33 size generally increased with RDA value, this relationship was not entirely consistent. Finally,
34 it was revealed that the aggregate size of pastes and their density also affected the friction and
35 wear of the fillings.

36 **Keywords**

37 Wear particle analysis, abrasive wear, friction, toothpaste, toothbrush, dental fillings

38 1 INTRODUCTION

39 Oral hygiene began to gain prominence at the turn of the 19th and 20th centuries. Initially,
40 toothbrushing with toothpaste primarily focused on deodorizing and general hygiene. However,
41 after the Second World War, the emphasis shifted to preventing tooth decay [1].

42 Although recommendations for fluoride toothpastes have evolved and the market has expanded
43 to include fluoride-free options, fluoride toothpastes remain a crucial preventive tool in
44 combating the onset and progression of dental caries, especially in children [2]. It is essential
45 that children's toothpaste contains sufficient fluoride to prevent caries while minimizing
46 abrasive ingredients [3]. In addition to these preventive measures, therapeutic options for
47 treating carious lesions have broadened to include new tooth preparation techniques and
48 restorative materials, often in combination with other therapeutic procedures. There has also
49 been a notable improvement in the aesthetics of hard tissue restorations, with improving
50 material composition and achieving better biocompatibility with dental tissues [4]. These
51 advancements are linked to specific physicochemical properties that contribute to mechanical
52 resistance. While professional dental hygiene typically considers the distinct properties of
53 dental tissues and prosthetic materials, personal dental care often does not differentiate between
54 the filling or prosthetic materials and natural dental tissues.

55 The issue of wear of restorative materials is highly relevant today. This concern arises from
56 the transition away from traditional dental amalgam toward a variety of modern materials, such
57 as glass ionomers, compomers, and composites [5]. However, these newer materials require
58 specific application principles due to their distinct properties. Their different physico-chemical
59 characteristics compared to outdated amalgams have a direct impact on their stability and
60 resistance to chemical influences within the dental cavity.

61 In addition to internal biological factors, external factors play a significant role in the wear of
62 fillings. These include friction and wear on the fillings caused by dietary habits and chosen oral
63 hygiene practices. Therefore, it is crucial for both research and clinical practice to monitor
64 external influences that may negatively impact the stability of filling materials. Factors affecting
65 the wear of fillings include the choice of toothbrush and the toothpaste used.

66 Considering toothbrushes, one of the key influential factors is bristle stiffness, which is related
67 to both the number and diameter of the bristles. Brushes with thinner bristles, i.e. softer bristles,
68 exhibit a lower wear rate [6, 7]. The toothpaste applied to the toothbrush is also a critical
69 component of personal daily oral hygiene [8]. The effectiveness of toothpaste is influenced not
70 only by the abrasiveness of the particles, measured as relative dentin abrasivity (RDA), but also
71 by the nature of the toothbrush fibers and the cleaning technique used [9].

72 RDA is a standardized, dimensionless index that expresses the relative rate of dentin removal
73 caused by a toothpaste under standardized laboratory conditions according to ISO 11609 [10].
74 It reflects the combined effect of abrasive particle concentration, size, surface characteristics,
75 and chemical composition of toothpaste formulations [10,11]. Typical RDA values range from
76 0 to 250, with higher values indicating greater abrasivity toward dentin [10]. Although RDA
77 does not represent a direct physical material property, it integrates multiple contributing factors
78 into a single comparative parameter.

79 Regarding the toothpaste, the solid particles within these products can vary significantly in
80 shape, size, and aggregation behaviour. Consequently, there is no direct correlation between
81 RDA values and mechanical damage to hard dental tissues or prosthetic materials [11, 12].

82 The development of toothpaste containing abrasive particles is closely related to the assessment
83 of complex wear, where abrasiveness is only one contributing factor. The wear and friction
84 related properties of these abrasive particles are crucial. For instance, the morphology of solid
85 particles and their interactions can be influenced by changes in disintegration or aggregation.
86 This means that the materials used in toothpaste and the toothbrush bristles behave differently
87 under different conditions [13]. Studies have shown that round particles tend to produce lower
88 wear rates on tooth surfaces, whereas larger aggregates within the paste can lead to higher wear
89 rates [14]. In general, softer materials are less abrasive and result in gentler wear [14, 15].

90 When examining the friction coefficient, the particle sharpness is an important influencing
91 factor. It has been demonstrated that during simulated cleaning experiments, the friction
92 coefficient for dental surfaces with alumina and silica abrasives decreases during the first ten
93 minutes. This is followed by a process where the particles become rounded, ultimately reaching
94 a steady state value for the friction coefficient [16].

95 Consistent preclinical modelling of friction and wear is important not only for predicting
96 the integrity of various dental materials but also for evaluating the impact of friction and wear
97 on the quality of the filling in contact with hard dental tissues. Monitoring the resistance of hard
98 dental tissues, as well as restorative and prosthetic materials, requires an approach that
99 incorporates techniques such as tribometry, interferometry, and scanning electron microscopy,
100 in addition to tribology [7, 17]. Understanding how abrasive particles interact with dental
101 surfaces under realistic brushing conditions is therefore crucial for improving both restorative
102 materials and toothpaste formulations.

103 Despite extensive research on the abrasivity of toothpastes in relation to enamel and dentin,
104 the tribological response of restorative filling materials to toothpaste brushing remains
105 relatively underexplored. Restorative materials differ substantially from natural dental tissues
106 in composition, microstructure, and mechanical behaviour, and their interaction with abrasive
107 particles cannot be directly inferred from enamel- or dentin-based studies. As a result, current
108 toothpaste abrasivity metrics, including RDA, provide limited guidance regarding their impact
109 on restorative surfaces.

110 Previous studies have primarily focused on correlating RDA values with the wear of enamel or
111 dentin. The issue of these studies is that toothpastes with high RDA values often demonstrate
112 better cleaning efficiency while having the same or greater abrasive effects [18, 19]. Although
113 effective toothpaste formulations are being developed to minimize wear while maintaining
114 cleaning efficacy, the tribological behaviour of dental restoration materials remains
115 insufficiently researched. This knowledge gap complicates the development of toothpastes that
116 are both effective and gentle on the surface of dental restorations. Understanding the role of
117 abrasive particles in the wear of filling materials is therefore essential for improving toothpaste
118 formulations and the long-term effectiveness of dental restorations.

119 In contrast to previous studies primarily focused on enamel or dentin, this study targets
120 restorative filling materials and examines their tribological response. By analysing time-
121 resolved friction behaviour and volumetric wear, it provides new insights into particle-driven
122 tribological mechanisms relevant to modern restorative dentistry.

123 **Therefore, the aim of this study is to investigate how the morphology, size, and**
124 **aggregation behaviour of abrasive particles influence the friction and wear of selected**
125 **dental filling materials under simulated toothbrushing conditions.** In this work, we
126 specifically address the **wear aspect** of this complex problem as a **first step** toward a more
127 comprehensive evaluation that will later also include cleaning efficiency. By first characterizing
128 how abrasive particle properties affect tribological behaviour independently of RDA values,
129 these findings represent a first stage in the broader effort to identify and develop **low-abrasive,**
130 **high-efficiency toothpastes** capable of preserving both natural dental tissues and restorative
131 surfaces.

132 **2 MATERIALS AND METHODS**

133 **2.1 Experimental Apparatus**

134 Tribological experiments to evaluate the friction coefficients over time were performed on
135 a Bruker TriboLab UMT tribometer (Bruker Corporation, USA). A key feature of this device is
136 its interchangeable bottom modules, which allow for the adjustment of experimental conditions.
137 In this study, a reciprocal module was used to facilitate a reciprocating motion with a preset
138 amplitude and frequency for the holder containing the dental filling sample. A toothbrush was
139 positioned above the sample in a stationary manner (Figure 1). The upper part of the device
140 comprises the probes equipped with sensitive sensors that record friction and normal forces,
141 allowing for the observation of the time course of the friction coefficient.

142 **2.2 Contact Pair and Lubricant**

143 The overall brushing process was experimentally simulated using a tribological system, where
144 the contact pair consisted of toothbrush bristles and the surface of a dental filling material fixed
145 in a holder. AS solution, combined with the selected toothpaste, was poured into the holder (see
146 Figure 1).

149 All dental filling samples were fabricated using a layering technique (Figure 2) and cured with
150 a UV lamp (Ledex WL 090, Woodpecker, China). The samples measured 9.5 x 9.5 x 3 mm,
151 and the worn layer made of a light-cured compomer material, Dyract Flow Shade A2 (Dentsply
152 Sirona, USA). For the subsequent three layers of the filling, the nanocomposite material Filtek
153 Ultimate 3920 A1B (3M, USA) was utilized. Each layer was UV cured for 20 seconds after
154 application.

155

156

Figure 2: Material layers of the sample

157 2.3 Tribological Setup

158 Table 1 presents the toothbrush used in the experiments, materials and toothpastes selected
159 along with their RDA values. RDA values reported in Table 1 were obtained by the
160 manufacturers upon request.

161 A Curaprox Ultra Soft 5460 (Curaden AG, Switzerland) manual toothbrush was used in all
 162 experiments. According to manufacturer specifications, the brush head contains approximately
 163 5 460 ultra-fine Curen® filaments with a filament diameter of approximately 0.10 mm.
 164 Filaments are densely packed to form a compliant and distributed contact with the surface. The
 165 approximate brush head dimensions are 25 mm × 10 mm. Due to the high filament density and
 166 low filament stiffness, the contact between the toothbrush and the filling surface can be
 167 considered as a distributed multi-asperity contact.

168 A total of seven sets of measurements were taken, with three repetitions for each set to ensure
 169 the credibility of the experiments. Four adult toothpastes with different levels of abrasiveness
 170 (RDA) and two children’s toothpastes were utilized during the measurements. Artificial saliva
 171 (AS) serving as a reference in the experiments. One toothbrush was used per experiment.

172 Table 1: Selected toothbrush, dental filling material and toothpastes with RDA values:

Toothbrush	Filling material	Type of the mixture	Values of RDA
		Colgate total whitening (Colgate TW) + AS (Colgate-Palmolive, USA)	142
		Sensodyne Extra Fresh Repair and Protect (Sensodyne EFRP) + AS (Haleon, UK)	85
Curaprox Ultra Soft 5 460	Dyract Flow Shade A2 – worn layer	Herbadent + AS (Herbadent, Czechia)	38
	Filtek Ultimate 3920 A1B – 3 body layers	Elmex Sensitive + AS (Colgate-Palmolive, USA)	30
		Weleda + AS (Weleda AG, Switzerland)	15
		Children's dental gel Benjamínek (Nobilis Tilia, Czechia) + AS	NA
		AS	-

173 *Note: RDA values were obtained from manufacturers upon request; RDA values for Benjamínek toothpaste are not*
 174 *specified.*

175 The experimental measurements of the friction coefficient were conducted on tribometer Bruker
176 UMT TriboLab. The tribometer's sensors recorded both normal and frictional forces, from
177 which the friction coefficient was recorded over time. For the experiments, a reciprocal module
178 with a track length of 10 mm and a frequency of 2 Hz was configured to ensure that
179 the toothbrush cleaned the entire surface of the sample during the movement. This reciprocating
180 frequency corresponds to approximately 120 brushing strokes per minute, which is
181 representative of manual toothbrushing conditions reported in the literature [18].
182 The toothbrush was fixed in a static pin, and a load force of 4 N was applied to the filling during
183 the brushing simulation, based on previous experimental studies (Figure 1) [6]. While manual
184 toothbrushes typically exert a clamping force of around 2.5 N [18], a value of 4 N was chosen
185 to achieve more significant wear.

186 During the experiment, the filling sample was secured in the holder using a clamping screw on
187 the support plate to ensure the contact between the specimen and the toothbrush (see
188 Figure 1 a)). The holder was filled with a slurry of toothpaste and AS (1 g of toothpaste and
189 5 ml of saliva), which was heated to 37 °C using two heating cartridges inserted into the holder
190 (see Figure 1 a)). The slurry was added to the holder both at the beginning and in the middle of
191 the experiments (at 130 min). Throughout the brushing experiment, the edges of the filling
192 sample were covered to establish reference levels (Figure 3), which later played an important
193 role in the evaluation of volume loss.

194 The total duration of the experiment was set at 260 min, corresponding to the brushing time for
195 one tooth surface over 8.5 years, assuming a daily contact of the toothbrush with one tooth for
196 5 seconds [12, 18]. This value is somewhat exaggerated as it reflects 3 minutes of brushing
197 twice a day. However, under normal conditions, it is recommended to brush twice a day for
198 2 minutes [20]. If we recalculate the time on all tooth surfaces, a period of 8.5 years
199 (260 minutes) corresponds to a toothbrush replacement interval of approximately 45 days. In
200 the study [18], 72 surfaces were created, and considering a maximum cleaning time of 5 seconds
201 per day per surface, the total time of the experiment was 270 minutes. In order to approximate
202 this time while maintaining the accuracy, an experiment duration of 260 min was established,
203 with the sample filling surface representing approximately one tooth surface.

204 **2.4 Evaluation of Friction Coefficient**

205 The coefficient of friction was calculated from the measured normal and friction forces
206 measured by the tribometer. The friction force was recorded as the lateral force component
207 (F_x), while the applied normal load corresponded to F_z . The UMT TriboLab software calculated
208 the friction force magnitude as $F_f = |F_x|$. Consequently, the instantaneous coefficient of friction
209 was determined as $\mu(t) = |F_{x(t)}| / F_{z(t)}$. In reciprocating motion, the sign of F_x reverses with the
210 sliding direction; however, this sign change reflects only the kinematic direction of motion and
211 does not represent a change in friction magnitude. Therefore, the coefficient of friction is
212 reported as a positive quantity corresponding to the absolute friction force.

213 The raw data were exported in CSV format and downsampled for graphical representation to
214 reduce data density and improve figure readability. This post-processing step was applied solely
215 for visualization purposes and did not affect the overall friction trends.

216 Consequently, from the seven sets of measurements (six toothpastes and reference
217 measurements with artificial saliva), three friction–time curves were obtained for each set.
218 An average time course was calculated from the three repeated measurements within each set
219 and is presented in Figure 5.

220 The data were plotted as a time series to capture the long-term evolution of friction during
221 brushing. Although the motion was reciprocating, the frequency was constant, making time and
222 brushing cycle number directly proportional. A time-based representation was therefore chosen
223 to improve clarity and to allow direct correlation with experimental events, such as slurry
224 addition, as well as with the phase-averaged CoF values shown in Figure 6.

225 2.5 Wear Analysis and Evaluation

226 Volume loss was determined using a Bruker GT-X optical profilometer (Bruker Corporation,
227 USA) based on vertical scanning interferometry (VSI). A 5x magnification objective was
228 chosen for the measurements (see Figure 3 a)). Topographies of the samples were obtained by
229 stitch scanning over an area of 10 x 10 mm at a scan depth of 100 nm using white light. Before
230 and after each brushing simulation, the filling sample was scanned with the optical profilometer
231 to facilitate volume subtraction and further evaluation of material volume loss using Vision 64
232 software.

233 For the scans of the surfaces before and after brushing (see Figure 3), noise was removed using
234 the *Mask Data* function (see Figure 3 b)). Surface levelling was then performed using the *Terms*
235 *Removal* function by fitting a first-order polynomial (plane) to the unworn reference regions,
236 while the worn area was masked to prevent distortion of the reference plane. The unworn
237 reference regions were subsequently unmasked and used to define the zero level of the surface
238 (Figure 3c). Missing or invalid data points, visible as isolated black regions after leveling, were
239 reconstructed using the *Data Restore* function based on local neighbourhood averaging with
240 a restoration window size of 20 data points (Figure 3d).

241 To separate surface roughness from form and waviness, an ISO-compliant *Gaussian filter* was
242 applied during surface processing. The cutoff wavelength (λ_c) was selected according to EN
243 ISO 4288 based on the roughness parameter R_z measured on the worn surface [21]. A cutoff
244 wavelength of $\lambda_c = 0.8$ mm was applied consistently to all datasets (Figure 3e).

245 In all experiments, a part of the sample was covered to established reference zero levels, which
246 were used to align the sample surface and to subtract material volume loss. The volume loss
247 was subsequently evaluated for a surface area of $55 \pm 2 \text{ mm}^2$ using Vision 64 software.

248

249 Figure 3: Sample scanned on the optical profilometer (a), surface after removing the noise with Mask Data
250 function (b), flattening of the surface using Terms removal function (c), Data restoration (d), smoothing
251 by Gaussian regression filter (e), Mask Data function (f), sample worn area with plastic cover and wear
252 details in X- profile section (g)

253 2.6 Particle Morphology and Surface Elemental Analysis

254 The toothpaste samples for scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analysis were placed in tubes
255 and diluted with water at a volume ratio of 1:3. Subsequently, the tubes were manually mixed
256 for approximately 10 minutes to ensure optimal dissolution of the pastes in the water.
257 The primary objective of this procedure was to ensure that the abrasive particles would not
258 dissolve in the water, while other additives (such as polymers and low molecular weight
259 substances) would. After partial dissolution, a suspension was created; this was then centrifuged
260 (MicroStar12, VWR, USA) at 13.5 rpm for 5 minutes (see Figure 4 a) and b)).
261 The centrifugation process was repeated four times.

262 Following preparation, the surfaces of the samples were coated with a 15 nm gold layer (Figure
263 4 c)) using the EM ACE 600 (Leica Microsystems, Wetzlar, Germany). Toothpaste morphology
264 was investigated using a scanning electron microscope (Tescan MIRA3, Czech Republic). All
265 observations were made in the backscattered electron emission mode at an acceleration voltage
266 of 10 kV. The scan mode was set to DEPTH, and the beam density was adjusted to 10.
267 The working distance was set to 15 mm.

268 Surface elemental analysis was conducted using energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX,
269 Oxford Instruments, England) and evaluated with Aztec 2.1a software to reveal the presence of
270 abrasives in the pastes through the weight percentages of the corresponding elements.
271 The measurement was performed as an evaluation of the energy spectrum of the emitted
272 photons (each element has unique energy values), where each peak corresponded to a specific
273 element [22]. A quantitative analysis further determined the types of abrasives present in
274 the pastes based on mass composition. Particle size and distribution were calculated using
275 ImageJ software from SEM images taken at a magnification of 200kx and averaged from
276 100 measurements.

277

278 Figure 4: Centrifuge MicroStar 12 (VWR, USA) (a), separation of organic and inorganic components after
279 the centrifugation (b), samples coated with gold deposited on the carbon strips (c)

280 **3 RESULTS**

281 **3.1 Coefficient of Friction**

282 For CoF, seven time histories were obtained from seven sets of measurements. Each set
283 consisted of three repeated brushing experiments performed under identical nominal test
284 conditions. Consequently, three individual friction–time histories were acquired for each
285 toothpaste and for the reference artificial saliva (AS). An average time history was calculated
286 from the three repetitions for each set, as described in Chapter 2.4. The slurry of AS with the
287 selected paste was always added to the holder at the beginning and again in the middle of the
288 experiments (130 min). The results of the CoF time histories with the addition of the AS paste
289 slurry can be seen in Figure 5.

290

291 Figure 5: CoF as a function of time with the addition of toothpaste and saliva slurry in the middle of each
292 experiment

293 More fluctuations in CoF values were observed in the first half of the experiment. When
294 a second slurry of AS paste was added, the CoF values converged to a steady state; however,
295 fluctuations in CoF values over time were observed in all cases. The individual friction curves
296 obtained from repeated experiments showed considerable variability between individual trials,
297 despite identical nominal test conditions. This variability results from the statistical nature of
298 abrasive particle entrainment and discontinuous particle contact with the surface during
299 brushing. The smoothest friction–time response was obtained for the AS reference, which can
300 be attributed to the absence of abrasive particles; in this case, AS without paste was also added
301 in the middle of the experiment.

302 For each toothpaste and the AS reference, mean values were calculated from three repeated
303 experiments over defined time intervals of approximately 85 min per phase. The friction curves
304 shown in Figure 5 represent averaged responses as a function of time, while Figure 6
305 summarizes the corresponding mean values and standard deviations for divided time intervals
306 of equal duration. Phase A (0–86.5 min) corresponds to the running-in phase, during which the
307 actual contact area progressively develops. This phase is characterized by higher variability and
308 generally increased CoF values (Figure 5) due to the initial sharpness of the abrasive particles,
309 reflecting surface adaptation processes rather than fully stabilized friction response. Phase B
310 (86.5–173 min) represents a transition regime. The addition of abrasive particles and lubricating
311 components changes the contact conditions and may lead to fluctuations in the coefficient of
312 friction. Due to the stochastic nature of particle entrainment and discontinuous particle–surface
313 interactions, CoF values remain variable during this stage. Phase C (173–259.5 min)
314 corresponds to the phase after prolonged sliding in the presence of the slurry, when the
315 tribological response becomes relatively more stable.

316

317

Figure 6: Average values of CoF: A – running-in phase, B – the middle phase, C - the end phase (CoF results were measured in triplicate for each toothpaste, divided into mentioned phases and shown as mean \pm standard deviation)

318

319

320

For most pastes, CoF values were higher during the running-in phase than in the final phase, except for Weleda paste, where time courses of CoFs varied considerably from experiment to experiment. In the middle of the experiment, a second AS paste slurry was added, however, the experiment continued without interruption, which is related to the fact that not all particles could have come into direct contact. As a result, CoF values became quite variable, depending on how much and whether abrasive particles came into contact, as previously mentioned.

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326 3.2 Dental Filling Volume Loss

327 The evaluated graphical results of material loss represent a total of seven values, each of which
328 is an average of three experiments \pm standard deviation (SD). In the case of wear measurements,
329 low deviations were not achieved even with repeated measurements. The evaluation of volume
330 loss is somewhat affected by human error, as the parameters being evaluated are very small.
331 However, for both friction and wear, the main factors influencing the results are whether
332 the particles come into direct contact and whether they are deposited on the bristles. These
333 processes are uncontrollable during the measurement, which is why the deviation values are
334 relatively high. The volume loss values for all sets are shown in Figure 7.

335

336 Figure 7: Average volume losses of measured pastes ranked with decreasing RDA (results of volume losses were
337 measured in triplicate for each toothpaste and shown as mean \pm standard deviation)

338 The Colgate TW paste exhibited the highest volume loss value. This paste also had the highest
339 RDA value (142), which would correspond with the maximum wear effect observed. In
340 contrast, the minimum volume loss values were recorded for the reference measurements with
341 AS and for children's dental gel Benjamínek.

342 **3.3 Evaluation of Particle Morphology and Surface Elemental Analysis of Paste**

343 For imaging the morphology of abrasive particles in this study, magnifications of 500x and 5kx
344 were chosen. Figures 8 and 9 display the morphology of the abrasive particles from each paste
345 at the specified magnifications.

346

347 Figure 8: Particle morphology visualized by SEM ((Tescan MIRA3, Czech Republic, magnified 500x): a) Colgate
348 TW, b) Sensodyne EFRP, c) Herbadent, d) Elmex Sensitive, e) Weleda, f) Benjamínek

349

350 Figure 9: Particle morphology visualized by SEM (Tescan MIRA3, Czech Republic, magnified 5kx): a) Colgate TW,
351 b) Sensodyne EFRP, c) Herbadent, d) Elmex Sensitive, e) Weleda, f) Benjamínek

352 In addition to the investigation of particle morphology, the elemental analysis was also
353 performed using an EDX detector of SEM. For the visual representation of the results from the
354 elemental analysis, only one paste was selected; however, all results are presented in Table 2.
355 The results were obtained as mass fractions of the elements in the measured paste sample.
356 Figure 10 displays the elemental analysis of the Sensodyne EFRP, revealing that the dominant
357 abrasive component is hydrated silica.

358

359 Figure 10: Mass composition of elements in Sensodyne EFRP paste (results were measured in triplicate for each
 360 toothpaste and shown as mean \pm standard deviation)

361 Subsequently, the average particle sizes were evaluated as shown in Figure 11. Particle size was
 362 averaged from 100 values \pm SD. It can be observed that the wear values increased with
 363 the particle size of pastes.

364

365 Figure 11: Average sizes of abrasive particles (results were measured from 100 values for each toothpaste and
 366 shown as mean \pm standard deviation)

367 Table 2 summarizes information on the type of abrasive particles evaluated by EDX.
 368 Additionally, the table includes the average particle sizes for each paste, a description of
 369 the particle shapes at different microscopic magnifications (Figures 6 and 7), and details of
 370 particle aggregation.

371 Table 2: Summary table of elemental composition and properties of particles:

	Abrasive Particles	Particle Size [nm]	Shape	Arrangement
Colgate TW	silica, calcium pyrophosphate, coal powder	32 ± 6	round particles, aggregates - more rounded edges	small and medium aggregations
Sensodyne EFRP	silica, titanium dioxide	30 ± 8	elongated and round particles, aggregates - sharper shapes	small and medium aggregations with lower density
Herbadent	silica	25 ± 5	round particles, aggregates - sharper shapes	small and medium aggregations
Elmex Sensitive	silica	27 ± 5	round particles, aggregates - more rounded edges	small and medium aggregations (occasionally large)
Weleda	silica	25 ± 6	round particles, aggregates - more rounded edges	small and medium aggregations (occasionally large)
Benjamínek	silica	25 ± 5	round particles, aggregates - sharper shapes	small and medium aggregations

372 As shown in the table, all toothpastes contain silica as an abrasive compound. Colgate TW
 373 toothpaste had the largest particle size, while children's toothpastes and Herbadent toothpaste
 374 had the smallest particles. Since all the pastes contained the same dominant abrasive particle,
 375 the shape of the particles was primarily round. The aggregations were relatively random in
 376 shape and reached a size of up to 20 μm.

377 4 DISCUSSION

378 As can be seen in the results section, the smoothest time course was obtained for AS, which is
379 attributed to the absence of abrasive particles. AS without paste was also added in this case in
380 the middle of the experiment. Overall, we observed that the time courses exhibited quite a lot
381 of variability. This randomness is related to our inability to predict how many particles are in
382 direct contact [19] at any given time, as well as the varying shapes and sizes of particle
383 aggregations in individual pastes. When particles aggregate into larger units, friction and wear
384 tend to increase because more load is transferred [14, 23]. However, the presence of such
385 aggregates in the contact is not continuous, resulting in time-dependent friction responses that
386 do not follow a uniform or steady pattern. For this reason, the coefficient of friction was
387 evaluated as a function of time. CoF curves plotted over time reveal the variability of friction
388 associated with discontinuous particle contact and provide information that cannot be obtained
389 from average values alone.

390 In previous chapters, we noted that during the running-in(A) and middle (B) phases of the time
391 courses, mixtures of AS and paste were introduced into the experiment. It is important to note
392 that the experiment was not paused during the lateral addition in phase B; thus, the mixture
393 could dissolve in the sample bath, potentially preventing a direct contact between the brush and
394 the filling. In such cases, higher coefficient values for phase A would be expected. Conversely,
395 if the particles come into contact, this will manifest itself as an increase in the time course
396 similar to the one observed at the beginning of the measurement. In this case, the average CoF
397 values would peak during the middle phase (B). In the final phase (C), particles may either
398 abrade or adhere to the brush bristles, resulting in a lack of direct contact and subsequently
399 lower CoF values. This pattern is consistent, except for the Weleda paste, where the overall
400 time courses were highly variable.

401 To reduce variation in the overall CoF measurements and maintain more stable friction
402 coefficient values, consideration should be given to shortening the interval for adding the paste-
403 saliva slurry. Additionally, to increase the likelihood of direct particle contact with the tooth
404 filling surface, it may be beneficial to avoid the mixture being applied laterally during
405 the experiment. Instead, one could either abort the experiment or modify the holder design to
406 allow for direct application of the mixture.

407 The results indicate that the volume loss values for the fillings increased with the RDA value.
408 Colgate TW, with RDA of 142, exhibited the highest wear values and contained the most
409 abrasive particle types of relatively large sizes. In contrast, Benjamínek children's dental gel
410 showed the lowest volume loss values as its aggregates were primarily small and more rounded
411 with smaller particle sizes.

412 In the case of children's toothpastes, wear values were lower, likely due to the presence of less
413 abrasive particles. Generally, the sweet taste of children's toothpastes encourages children to
414 brush for longer, which is beneficial for dental health as it helps prevent dental caries [3].
415 Fluoride is a key component in many toothpastes promoting remineralisation and increasing the
416 surface resistance to wear [23]. However, due to the sweet taste, children may tend to swallow
417 the toothpaste, which can lead to fluorosis, characterized by white and brown stains on the teeth
418 [24]. In our study, the children's tooth gels did not contain fluoride. However, the oils present
419 in both pastes contribute to a lower paste viscosity, which, together with a lower concentration
420 of abrasives, may be associated with reduced friction and wear.

421 The results showed that the particle size had a significant effect on wear. As particle size
422 increases, volume loss also tends to increase. This relationship is due to the RDA values, which
423 reflect the size of the abrasive particles; therefore, larger abrasive particles should correspond
424 to higher RDA values [25]. However, this trend did not hold for the Herbadent paste. Our focus
425 on a specific sample of the paste may introduce some inaccuracies. The measurement error in
426 the wear experiments is relatively high. Given that the wear values are quite small, a human
427 error in evaluation is likely to contribute to this variation. Additionally, as previously
428 mentioned, the presence of particles in direct contact, which can vary significantly during
429 measurements, plays a significant role [19]. To maximize the particle contact, a reciprocating
430 motion and a fine brush were chosen for the experiments. The reciprocating motion is expected
431 to capture more particles than the rotating motion. The Curaprox Ultra fine brush was selected
432 because its softer bristles deform well, allowing for a more homogeneous distribution of
433 particles at their tips [19].

434 Colgate TW paste exhibited the highest wear values, likely due to its maximum particle size,
435 relatively high particle density, and random or round shapes of aggregates. As shown in
436 Figure 7, the wear values of Herbadent and Elmex Sensitive were only slightly different. These
437 toothpastes also had similar RDA values, Elmex Sensitive 30, and Herbadent 38. Sensodyne
438 EFRP, with an RDA value of 85, had relatively low wear values compared to these pastes.
439 Furthermore, the average CoF for both Herbadent and Elmex Sensitive was higher than that of
440 Sensodyne EFRP, despite their higher RDA values. The lowest friction and wear values were
441 observed for the Benjamínek children's dental gel. These low values can be attributed to the
442 aggregate density, which was notably low for both Sensodyne EFRP and Benjamínek children's
443 dental gel as shown in Figure 8. This low aggregate density means that fewer particles are in
444 direct contact with surfaces; with saliva being the primary contact. In contrast, the Elmex
445 Sensitive paste contained relatively large aggregates that could increase wear due to their
446 sharpness [14].

447 A surface elemental analysis was performed using the EDX analysis to evaluate the energy
448 spectrum of emitted photons, where each peak corresponded to a specific element composition
449 of the tested pastes. This analysis provides both qualitative and quantitative data regarding the
450 type and mass amount of the specific element present [22]. Unlike X-ray photoelectron
451 spectroscopy (XPS), EDX does not provide information on the bonds between elements [26].
452 Therefore, the composition of the abrasive particles in the pastes was estimated on the basis of
453 the EDX analysis combined with manufacturers' specifications. For instance, Figure 9 illustrates
454 several elements present in Sensodyne EFRP toothpaste. The presence of abrasives such as
455 calcium carbonate or calcium phosphate can explain these elements. Only Colgate TW and
456 Sensodyne EFRP pastes contained elements other than oxygen, silicon, and carbon, which is
457 consistent with manufacturers' claims of additional abrasives in these formulations.

458 Other properties of the abrasive particles, such as hardness [27], also have a significant effect
459 on friction and wear during cleaning processes; however, this was not part of our study.
460 Additionally, toothbrush characteristics such as stiffness and bristle count or diameter could
461 also play a role in wear. Some studies have shown that a harder toothbrush increased tooth
462 surface wear [6], while others suggest little or no correlation with wear [7, 28, 29].

463 Different types of filling materials with different mechanical properties also have a significant
464 impact on wear. In this study, we used Dyract Flow Shade, a compomeric material known for
465 its good biocompatibility but higher susceptibility to wear [30]. The relatively low wear values
466 observed suggest that it would be preferable to select a material more likely to exhibit wear.

467 All experiments were conducted under simulated conditions without accounting for the
468 continuous demineralisation and remineralization that occurs in dental cavities due to food and
469 drinks. These processes can erode enamel structure, expose surfaces and increase the risk of
470 wear. The pH value of the tooth surface fluctuates based on nutrition and oral hygiene practices.
471 Toothpastes containing remineralising agents, especially fluoride, can help to remineralize the
472 tooth surface after cleaning and increase pH levels after consumption, thereby reducing
473 susceptibility to wear [13, 31]. The pH of toothpastes is standardised at 5.5 to prevent
474 demineralization since the critical pH range for tooth surfaces is between 5.1 and 5.5 [27].
475 Future research could study the effectiveness of toothpastes containing remineralising agents
476 and their effect on wear of dental fillings.

477 5 CONCLUSIONS

478 This study investigated how the properties of abrasive particles in toothpastes affect the friction
479 and wear of selected restorative material used in dentistry. The tribological experiments were
480 conducted based on the reciprocal direct contact between a toothbrush and a tooth filling in
481 a solution of the investigated toothpaste mixed with artificial saliva. During the brushing
482 simulation, the CoF was analysed, and after the measurements, the wear of the dental filling
483 was assessed using optical methods. Particle morphology was analysed from SEM analysis, and
484 elemental composition was determined by EDX analysis. In contrast to previous studies, which
485 focused mostly on dentin and enamel wear, our findings highlight several important conclusions
486 regarding selected dental fillings:

- 487 • CoF time courses are variable and influenced by the presence of particles in direct contact.
- 488 • Filling wear increases with particle size, aggregate size, sharpness, and particle density.
- 489 • Maximum filling wear values were observed for Colgate TW paste, which corresponds to
490 its highest RDA value and its whitening properties.
- 491 • Children's dental gels showed the lowest wear rates.

492 The experimental methodology presented in this study provides a solid basis for evaluating the
493 tribological behaviour of dental materials under simulated toothbrushing conditions. By
494 integrating assessments of cleaning efficiency, these studies will enable a more complete
495 understanding of toothpaste performance. Unlike studies focused on dentin/enamel, this work
496 provides a reproducible methodology for testing restorative materials and establishes
497 a foundation for developing low-abrasive, high-efficiency toothpastes that protect restorative
498 materials, highlighting the novelty and practical relevance of this research for advancing oral
499 care strategies.

500 **Credit Authorship Contribution Statement**

501 M. Vrbka, P. Formánková and P. Svoboda conceived the idea. P. Formánková, V. Pavliňáková,
502 P. Čípek, L. Vojtová and M. Vrbka designed the experiments. P. Formánková and V.
503 Pavliňáková performed the experiments and analysed the data. P. Formánková, V. Pavliňáková
504 and P. Svoboda wrote the original draft of the manuscript. M. Vrbka and L. Vojtová revised the
505 manuscript. M. Vrbka and A. Dančová administrated the projects and secured the funding. M.
506 Vrbka supervised the study. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

507

508 **Declaration of Competing Interest**

509 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
510 relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

511

512 **Data Availability**

513 Data will be made available on request.

514

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526

527 **Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted Technologies in the Writing Process**

528 During the preparation of this work the authors used Grammarly and DeepL in order to improve
529 the language quality and increase readability. After using these tools, the authors reviewed and
530 edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

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